

Stereospecific Synthesis of Pipericide and 10,11-Dihydropipericide

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Natural (*E*) and (*E,E*)-conjugated dienamide (1) and 10,11-dihydropipericide (2) have been synthesised via Wittig and Li_2CuCl_4 catalysed coupling reactions of alkyl halides and Grignard reagents.

(*2E,4E*)-Dienamides constitute an important class of compounds found especially in the Compositae, Piperaceae and Rutaceae families and possess insecticidal activity, generally embraced within a structure^{1,2}. They are accessible in only very small amounts from natural sources and therefore synthetic approaches to these rather unstable amides are required. 2(*E*),4(*E*)-Undecatrienoic isobutylamide carrying on 11-(3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl) substituent, pipericide (1), has been isolated from *Piper nigrum* and reported to be insecticidally active against the Adzuki bean-weevil (*Callosobruchus chinensis*)³. 10,11-Dihydropipericide (2) also occurs in *P. nigrum*⁴. Dihydropipericide is insecticidally active and synergises the activity of pipericide⁴. Literature reports stereoselective syntheses of pipericide and dihydropipericide via the corresponding

dienoate⁵, via thermal SO_2 extrusion from *cis*-2,5-disubstituted-2,5-dihydrothiophene-1,1-dioxides generated by a retro Diels-Alder reaction⁶. We report a simple and stereoselective synthesis via Wittig reaction and Li_2CuCl_4 catalysed coupling reaction of Grignard reagent with alkyl bromide in THF at -10° .

6-Tetrahydropyranyloxy-hexan-1-yl⁷ (Scheme 1) on subjection to Wittig reaction with (3',4'-methylenedioxyphenyl) methyltriphenylphosphonium bromide using dimesyl anion as a base in THF afforded 7-(3',4'-methylenedioxyphenyl)-1-tetrahydropyranyloxy-6(*E*)-heptene (3). Li_2CuCl_4 catalysed coupling⁸ reaction of piperonyl bromide with 1-tetrahydropyranyloxyhexylmagnesiumbromide (prepared from 6-bromo-1-tetrahydropyranyloxyhexane and activated Mg turnings) in THF under N_2 atmosphere

Scheme 1

furnished **4**. Depyration of **3** and **4** with PTS in methanol gave **5a** and **5b** which upon PCC oxidation in anhydrous CH_2Cl_2 afforded aldehydes **6a** and **6b**. Horner-Wittig reaction of aldehydes **6a** and **6b** with ethyl- γ -diethyl phosphonoacetate in diglyme/THF employing NaH as base afforded **7a** and **7b** respectively. Hydrolysis of esters **7a** and **7b** with 10% alcoholic KOH resulted in the formation of 11-(3',4'-methylenedioxyphenyl)-undeca-2(*E*),4(*E*),10(*E*)-trienoic acid (**8a**) and 11-(3',4'-methylenedioxyphenyl)-undeca-2(*E*),4(*E*)-dienoic acid (**8b**) which were condensed with isobutylamine using $\text{POCl}_3/\text{Et}_3\text{N}^\circ$ to give pipericide (**1**) and 10,11-dihydropipericide (**2**) respectively. Spectral data of the compounds **1** and **2** were in close agreement with that reported in literature⁵⁻⁷.

Experimental

Melting and boiling points are uncorrected. Ir spectra were run on a Perkin-Elmer 377 spectrophotometer and ^1H nmr spectra on a Varian EM-390 (90 MHz) spectrophotometer using TMS as an internal standard. Silica gel (ASC; Bombay) impregnated with CaSO_4 was used for tlc. Unless otherwise specified, all organic extracts were dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate.

7-(3',4'-Methylenedioxyphenyl)-1-(tetrahydropyranyloxy)-6(*E*)-heptene (3): To piperonyltriphenylphosphorane, prepared from piperonyltriphenylphosphoniumbromide (8.89 g, 20 mmol) in DMSO (25 ml) and sodium hydride (50%; 1.01 g, 42 mmol) under nitrogen atmosphere, was added 6-tetrahydropyranyloxy-hexan-1-ol (4 g, 20 mmol) in THF (10 ml) dropwise and the reaction mixture was stirred for 2 h and left overnight. The contents were heated at 50° for 30 min, poured into crushed ice, extracted with petroleum ether (4×50 ml), washed with water and dried. Removal of the solvent followed by distillation under reduced pressure of the residue afforded pure **3** (3.88 g, 61%); b.p. $150-52^\circ/6-7$ mm (Found: C, 71.45; H, 8.08. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_4$ requires: C, 71.67; H, 8.23%); ν_{max} 3 040, 1 640, 1 610, 1 220, 1 190, 1 116 and 970 cm^{-1} ; $\delta(\text{CCl}_4)$ 1.4-1.5 (12H, m, CH_2), 2.2 (2H, m, allylic CH_2), 3.3-3.7 (4H, m, CH_2 proton attached to C-1 of γ -pyrane and $2 \times \text{H-6}$ of γ -pyrane), 4.7 (1H, s, H-2 of γ -pyrane), 5.7 (1H, m, olefinic proton), 5.95 (2H, s, methylenedioxy proton), 6.2-6.4 (1H, d, olefinic proton) and 6.7-6.9 (3H, m, ArH).

7-(3',4'-Methylenedioxyphenyl)-1-(tetrahydropyranyloxy)-heptane (4): To the cooled Grignard reagent, prepared from dry magnesium turnings (0.40 g, 16 mmol) and 6-bromo-1-tetrahydropyranyloxyhexane (4.35 g, 16 mmol) in anhydrous THF (80 ml) under nitrogen atmosphere at -10° , was added piperonyl bromide (3.6 g, 16 mmol) in anhydrous THF (30 ml) dropwise. After stirring for 30 min, a catalytic amount of Li_2CuCl_4 (2 ml) in THF (10 ml) was added, stirred further for 4 h at the same temperature and left overnight. The reaction mixture was then quenched with NH_4Cl

solution, extracted with ether, washed with water and dried. Evaporation of the solvent followed by column chromatography of the crude material over silica gel using petroleum ether-ether as eluent afforded pure **4** (2.62 g, 50%) (Found: C, 71.03; H, 8.63. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_4$ requires: C, 71.25; H, 8.75%); ν_{max} 1 610, 1 190, 1 116 and $1 110\text{ cm}^{-1}$; $\delta(\text{CDCl}_3)$ 1.2-1.4 (18H, m, CH_2), 3.3-3.85 (4H, m, CH_2 proton attached to C-1 of γ -pyrane and $2 \times \text{H-6}$ of γ -pyrane), 4.6 (1H, s, H-2 of γ -pyrane), 6.0 (2H, s, methylenedioxy proton) and 6.7-6.9 (3H, s, ArH).

7-(3',4'-Methylenedioxyphenyl)-6(*E*)-heptanol (5a) and 7-(3',4'-methylenedioxyphenyl)-heptanol (5b): Compound **3** (3.18 g, 10 mmol)/**4** (3.20 g, 10 mmol) was dissolved in methanol (50 ml) containing PTS (250 mg) and the reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 10 h. Methanol was then removed under reduced pressure and the residue was diluted with water (10 ml), extracted with ether (3×50 ml), washed with 10% NaHCO_3 solution, water and dried. Solvent was evaporated and the residue was distilled under reduced pressure to give **5a** (1.29 g, 55%), b.p. $152-55^\circ/6-7$ mm (Found: C, 71.58; H, 7.52. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_3$ requires: C, 71.79; H, 7.69%); ν_{max} 3 380, 1 640, 1 050 and 970 cm^{-1} ; $\delta(\text{CCl}_4)$ 1.3-1.5 (6H, m, CH_2), 2.1-2.30 (2H, m, allylic CH_2), 3.6-3.8 (3H, m, CH_2OH), 5.72 (1H, m, olefinic proton), 6.0 (2H, s, methylenedioxy proton), 6.2-6.4 (1H, d, olefinic proton) and 6.72-7.0 (3H, m, ArH) and **5b** (1.25 g, 53%), $140-42^\circ/5-7$ mm (Found: C, 70.31; H, 8.39. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_3$ requires: C, 71.18; H, 8.47%); ν_{max} 3 400-3 340, 3 000, 1 610, 1 180, 1 120 and $1 100\text{ cm}^{-1}$; $\delta(\text{CDCl}_3)$ 1.2-1.5 (12H, m, CH_2), 2.7 (1H, bs, exchangeable with D_2O), 3.6-3.7 (2H, t, CH_2OH), 6.0 (2H, s, methylenedioxy proton) and 6.7-6.95 (3H, t, ArH).

7-(3',4'-Methylenedioxyphenyl)-6(*E*)-heptenal (6a) and 7-(3',4'-methylenedioxyphenyl)heptanal (6b): Pyridinium chlorochromate (4.80 g, 22 mmol)/(6.5 g, 30 mmol) and sodium acetate (250 mg) were suspended in dry CH_2Cl_2 (80 ml) and the contents were cooled to 5° . The alcohol (**5a**; 3.29 g, 14 mmol)/(**5b**; 4.72 g, 18 mmol) was added in a single lot to the reaction mixture and stirred for 2 h. The resulting solution was diluted with dry ether and filtered through neutral alumina. Solvent was evaporated and the residue distilled under reduced pressure to yield **6a** (2.23 g, 68.5%), b.p. $130-32^\circ/6-7$ mm (Found: C, 72.32; H, 6.71. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_3$ requires: C, 72.41; H, 6.89%); ν_{max} 2 980, 2 720, 1 715, 1 640, 1 610 and 970 cm^{-1} ; $\delta(\text{CDCl}_3)$ 1.25 (6H, s, CH_2), 2.35 (2H, m, allylic CH_2), 5.8-7.1 (7H, m, olefinic, methylenedioxy and ArH) and 9.5 (1H, s, CHO); and **6b** (3.1 g, 68%), b.p. $118-20^\circ/5-7$ mm (Found: C, 71.62; H, 7.48. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_3$ requires: C, 71.79; H, 7.7%); ν_{max} 3 000, 2 710, 1 715 and $1 610\text{ cm}^{-1}$; $\delta(\text{CDCl}_3)$ 1.2-1.4 (10H, m, CH_2), 6.0 (2H, s, methylenedioxy protons), 6.7-6.9 (3H, m, ArH) and 9.9 (1H, s, CHO).

11-(3',4'-Methylenedioxyphenyl)undeca-2(*E*),4(*E*),10(*E*)-trienoate (7a) and 11-(3',4'-methylenedioxy-

phenyl)-undeca-2(E),4(E)-dienoate (7b): Sodium hydride (1 g, 50%, 41 mmol)/(0.240 g, 50%, 10 mmol) pre-washed with dry n-hexane, was taken in diglyme (30 ml) and ethyl- γ -diethylphosphonocrotonate (5.5 g, 22 mmol/1.25 g, 5 mmol) was added dropwise at room temperature with constant stirring until gas evolution ceased. To the resulting clear solution was added the aldehyde (6a; 4.64 g, 20 mmol/6b; 1.18 g, 5 mmol) in dry THF (10 ml) slowly at 10°. Stirring was continued for 8 h at room temperature and then for 1.5 h at 50° and left overnight. The contents were poured into crushed ice, extracted thoroughly with ether (4 × 50 ml), washed with brine and dried. After evaporating the solvent, the crude product was chromatographed over neutral alumina using petroleum ether-ether (1:4) as eluent to afford 7a (4.85 g, 74%) (Found: C, 72.96; H, 7.22. C₂₀H₂₄O requires: C, 73.14; H, 7.31%); ν_{\max} 3 000, 2 910, 1 720, 1 650, 1 610, 985 and 960 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 0.85 (3H, t, CH₃), 1.30 (4H, m, CH₂), 1.82–2.1 (4H, m, allylic CH₂), 4.15 (2H, q, J 6Hz, OCH₂CH₃), 5.8–7.2 (11H, m, olefinic, aromatic) and 5.90 (2H, s, methylenedioxy proton); and 7b (1.16 g, 70%) (Found: C, 72.54; H, 7.69. C₂₀H₂₆O₄ requires: C, 72.72; H, 7.87%); ν_{\max} 2 900, 1 720, 1 640, 1 610, 985 and 970 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 0.85 (3H, t, CH₃), 1.2–1.33 (10H, m, CH₂), 1.95 (2H, m, allylic CH₂), 4.2 (2H, q, J 6Hz, OCH₂CH₃), 5.9–7.3 (9H, m, olefinic, methylenedioxy and ArH).

11-(3',4'-Methylenedioxyphenyl)-undeca-2(E),10(E)-trienoic acid (8a) and 11-(3',4'-methylenedioxyphenyl)-undeca-2(E),4(E)-dienoic acid (8b): To a well-stirred solution of the ester (7a; 3.28 g, 10 mmol)/(7b; 2.3 g, 7 mmol) in methanol (50 ml) was added 10% aqueous methanolic KOH (10 ml) and the contents were refluxed for 2 h. Methanol was then removed under reduced pressure and the residue diluted with water and extracted with ether (2 × 25 ml). The aqueous phase was acidified with dilute HCl, extracted with ether (4 × 25 ml) and dried. Evaporation of the solvent afforded pure acid 8a (2.34 g, 78%) (Found: C, 71.83; H, 6.43. C₁₈H₂₀O₄ requires: C, 72.0; H, 6.66%); ν_{\max} 3 400–3 000, 1 710, 1 640, 1 610, 990 and 960 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 1.3–1.6 (4H, m, CH₂), 2.0–2.2 (4H, m, allylic CH₂), 5.7–7.22 (11H, m, olefinic, methylenedioxy and ArH) and 10.0 (1H, bs, COOH); and 8b (1.62 g, 77%) (Found: C, 71.30; H, 7.12. C₁₈H₂₂O₄ requires: C, 71.52; H, 7.28%); ν_{\max} 3 400–3 000, 1 715, 1 640, 1 240, 1 080, 990, 970, 930 and 840 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 1.3–1.42 (10H, m, CH₂), 1.9–2.2 (2H, m, allylic CH₂), 5.8–7.2 (9H, m, olefinic, ArH), 6.1 (2H, s, methylenedioxy proton) and 11.0 (1H, s, COOH).

2(E),4(E),10(E)-Piperidine (1) and 10,11-dihydropiperidine (2): To a well-stirred and cold mixture of the acid (8a; 2 g, 6 mmol)/(8b; 1.60 g, 5 mmol), isobutylamine (0.9 g, 12 mmol)/(0.73 g, 10 mmol) and triethylamine (1.25 g, 12 mmol)/(1 g, 10 mmol) in dry CH₂Cl₂ (50 ml), was added POCl₃ (1.08 g)/(870 mg). After additional stirring for 10 min, Et₃N (2.2 g)/(1.50 g) was added. The stirring was continued at 0° for 1 h and then at room temperature for 30 min. The reaction mixture was extracted with ether, washed with water and dried. Evaporation of the solvent provided a gummy material which was crystallised to furnish pure 1 (1.71 g, 72.5%), m.p. 113–14° (Found: C, 74.09; H, 8.25; N, 3.85. C₂₂H₂₉NO₃ requires: C, 74.36; H, 8.61; N, 3.94%); ν_{\max} 3 290, 3 050, 2 850, 1 660, 1 645, 1 620, 1 360, 1 242, 1 220, 1 160, 1 030, 990, 930, 865 and 810 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 0.85 (6H, d, J 6Hz, CH(CH₃)₂), 1.3–1.8 (4H, s, CH₂ and 1H, CH(CH₃)₂), 2.0–2.4 (4H, m, allylic CH₂), 2.8–3.0 (2H, m, NHCH₂) and 5.7–7.2 (12H, m, olefinic, methylenedioxy, CONH and ArH); and 2 (1.23 g, 68.2%), m.p. 96–97° (Found: C, 73.75; H, 8.52; N, 3.80. C₂₂H₂₉NO₃ requires: C, 73.94; H, 8.68; N, 3.92%); ν_{\max} 3 090, 3 050, 2 845, 1 650, 1 620, 1 600, 1 440, 1 360, 1 242, 1 190, 1 160, 1 020, 990, 930 and 860 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 0.86 (6H, d, J 6Hz, CH(CH₃)₂), 1.2–1.6 (10H, m, CH₂ and 1H, CH(CH₃)₂), 2.03–2.3 (2H, m, allylic CH₂), 3.0–3.21 (2H, m, NHCH₂), 5.9–7.3 (10H, m, olefinic, methylenedioxy, CONH and ArH).

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